

Master's thesis presentation

“Carbon footprint assessment of leather waste adopting different possible treatment technologies using the Umberto tool”

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Workflow of the Presentation:

1. Introduction, problem, definition and objectives
2. Literature Review (on basis of data collection)
3. Materials and Methods (LCA methodology)
4. Results and Discussion
5. Conclusion
6. Recommendation (future possibilities)

Introduction:

- Solid waste from the leather industry poses a significant **environmental challenge** in developing countries like India, hindering sustainability in the leather sector.
- **Under utilisation** of these leather wastes leads to severe **socio-economic impacts** and **public health issues**.
- This signifies global waste share from developing countries.
- Over **half** of the leather waste comes from developing countries (UNIDO 2010).
- **Proper management** of leather waste is essential for environmental protection and improving socio-economic conditions.

Figure 1. Overview of waste generated by tanneries around the world (Popita et al. 2020).

Introduction:

- Sustainable **energy generation**, such as biofuel, offers a profitable and eco-friendly solution.
- Environmental burden **by emitting potential greenhouse gases (GHG)** into the atmosphere and pollutants into water and soil.
- The total emissions can be derived in the form of **total CO₂-eq**. The carbon footprint (**CF**) refers to the overall GHG released during the life cycle of a specific product, process, or service.
- According to Watch (2022), industrial emissions have been estimated at 4.5 gigatons of CO₂ equivalent. Accounting for 24% of total net greenhouse gas emissions, solely attributed to human activities (IPCC 2014).

(What is the primary objective or goal of this study?)

- To **identify and evaluate the possible treatment** methods by investigating **seven types** of leather waste.
- Each treatment was modelled in Umberto, employing IPCC 2021.
- **Carbon balance** through the treatment has been evaluated to calculate carbon emissions. **Only CO₂ emissions were calculated**; other greenhouse gases, such as those emitted during a few treatments, were not included.
- Identify the **suitable options** for each waste type based on **energy and mass recovery with their CF values**.
- Treatments based on output yields also depend on input and output percentages, as documented in the literature.
- **Compile** the results of the total CF for each treatment and **recommend for future** possibility.

Task Description

- To comprehensively **collect relevant scientific literature** on leather waste management and different treatment techniques adopted for the waste valorization to energy/value-added products
- To define the **system boundary** based on the goal definition of the LCA study
- To create a **data inventory** of necessary inputs and outputs for each stage in the identified system boundary above. Data can be obtained from primary sources such as an existing tannery or from secondary sources such as literature or databanks such as the Ecoinvent database.
- **Run the Umberto LCA+ tool** using the inventory created. Include simulations for different waste utilization scenarios.
- **Evaluate the emissions** associated with each process within the system boundary for the different scenarios created.
- Data **compilation** and **Result interpretation**.
- Providing recommendations for **best scenarios based on the minimum carbon footprint and product quantity/quality**.

Literature Review

Literature Review:

Type of leather waste –Only seven types of waste, in the literature, with available treatment perspectives and data for LCA analysis.

A. Raw trimmings

B. Hair waste

C. Fleshings

D. Chrome shavings

E. Buffing dust

F. Crust trimmings

G. Finishing waste

Figure 2. Different types of leather waste (A – G) as shown above.

Physicochemical behavior of different Leather waste

Table 1. Comparative view of different parameters for different leather waste (Average)

Parameters	Raw trimmings	Fleshings	Hair	Shavings/splits	Buffing dust	Crust trimmings	Finishing waste
pH	na	11-13	7.9	4.0-6.1	3.8-5.2	5.8	5.81
Moisture (%)	60-65	75-87	11-13.7	17-19.7	10.0-15.0	13	12-14
Total solids (%)	35-40	20-36	89	80.3-83	67.7	74.8	74.8
Volatile solids DM *(%)	55-63	75-82	90-91	71.3-88.8	67.7	74.8	72-76
Protein content (%)	21.5-26	5-7.2	72.8-75.0	61.6-63.9	54.5-57.5	na	na
Fat content (%)	4.25	7-18	2	2-5.0	1-4.5	4.2-6.9	4.2-6.9
Ash content (%)	-	6.1-8	10	10.5-15.0	10-12.8	7.9-8.1	7.9-8.1
Total chromium (%)	-	na	na	1.6-3.2	2.8-4.7	3.1	3.1-3.6
Carbon (%)	-	38.8-40.9 (40)	50-53.9 (52)	43	42.8-46.1	67.1	61-71
Oxygen (%)	na	36.7-41	22-26	41.3	38	7.24	7.24
Nitrogen (%)	-	11.3-11.6	16-18.3	8.4	7.0-10.3	9.76	7.76 -10
Hydrogen (%)	-	8.3	7	5.8	6.1	12.6	10.1-15.1
Sulfur (%)	-	0.6 -2.5	0.1-5	1.5	2.1	3.3	2-3-4.44
	(Masilamani et al. 2016)	(Kubendran et al. 2017; Ravindranath et al. 2010),	(Agustini et al. 2018; Da Souza et al. 2022),	(Velusamy et al. 2020; Gomes et al. 2019, Parisi et al. 2021)	(Yılmaz et al. 2007, Kiliç et al. 2020)	Same as finishing waste	(Velusamy et al. 2020)

*% on dry basis

Table 2. Literature review based upon LCA/non-LCA on leather waste

S. No.	Waste type	Scenarios	LCA	FU, Software &method	Model development	Goal
1	Raw trimmings					
	Sri Bala Kameswari et al. 2011	AD	X	na	✓	Utilization of input parameters
	Shakil, Ahmed et al. 2019	RECY	X	na	X	Utilization of raw trimmings for non-edible gelatin production
2	Fleshings					
	Mozhiarasi, Natarajan et al. 2023	AD	X	na	✓	Utilization of raw trimmings for biogas
	Hashem, Paul et al. 2024	CO	X	na	✓	Co-composting with chicken excreta, sawdust, and cow pats
	Amdouni, Trabelsi et al. 2021	Pyro	X	na	✓	Waste into high-value biofuels and biochars at 600°C
	Bianco, Panepinto et al. 2021	INCI	✓	1 kWh, SimaPro	✓	Waste to energy (MSW)
	Kiliç, Puig Vidal et al. 2014	RECY	✓	na	X	CF of biodiesel production
	Sandhya, Abinandan et al. 2016	RECY	X	na	✓	Biodiesel production
	Dufour, Iribarren 2012	RECY	✓	SimaPro	✓	Biodiesel production from different free fatty acid-rich wastes.
3	Hair waste					
	Barrena, Pagans et al. 2007	CO	X	na	✓	Co-composting with hair waste and sewage sludge (1:1)
	Menikpura, Premakumara 2021	LF	X	na	✓	Calculating emissions
	Agustini, Da Fontoura et al. 2018	AD	X	na	X	Examining the presence of hair waste with other leather wastes
	Ramya, Sathish et al. 2022	Keratin	X	na	✓	Extraction of keratin
4	Chrome shavings					
	Gomes et al. 2019	AD	X	na	✓	Utilization of raw trimmings for biogas
	Velusamy, Chakali et al. 2020	PYR	X	na	✓	Utilization chrome shavings (CS).
		INCI	X	na	✓	
	Senthil, Kavukcu et al. 2023	RECY	X	na	✓	utilization of chrome shavings as Natural polymer leather sheet
5	Buffing dust					
	Onur Yilmaz, I. Cem Kantarli et al. 2007	PYR	X	na	✓	Pyrolysis of buffing dust at 450°C and 600°C
6	Crust trimmings					
	Menikpura, Premakumara 2021	OD	X	na	✓	Calculating emissions
7	Leather finished trimmings (LFT)	INCI/PYR	X	na	✓	Same journal as mentioned in chrome shavings

AD-Anaerobic digestion, CO-Composting, OD -Open dumping, Pyr-Pyrolysis, INCI-Incineration

Model Development

Table 4. Overview of possible scenarios (treatment routes)

Treatments	Product recovery	Anaerobic digestion	Open dumping	Composting	Pyrolysis	Incineration
Raw Trimmings	Gelatin	✓	✓	-	-	-
Fleshings	Biodiesel	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
Hair waste	Keratin	-	✓	✓	-	-
Chrome shavings & splits	Leather sheet	✓	✓	-	✓	✓
Buffing dust	Leather board	-	✓	-	✓	-
Crust trimmings	-	-	✓	-	-	-
Finished trimmings	-	-	✓	-	✓	✓

- Model development will be discussed with respective results

Possible treatments for Leather wastes

- Anaerobic digestion (AD)

1. AD process is a biological treatment method in which **organic components** from leather waste are broken down by **anaerobic microorganisms**.
2. AD process has several disadvantages: it requires high power costs, produces sludge with poor dewatering ability post-AD, is highly sensitive to changes in temperature and feedstock, and under mesophilic conditions, there is a risk of pathogenic organism destruction.
3. In current study, raw trimmings, fleshings* and chrome shavings have been considered for this treatment.

- Composting

1. Composting is the natural process of **decomposing organic materials** into nutrient-rich soil amendment.
2. In the current study, fleshings and hair waste were examined to determine the total carbon emissions during composting treatment (Hashem et al. 2024).
3. Total emissions have been calculated based on **the total carbon percentages in input and output** compost (Boldrin et al. 2011).

Figure 3. The general process of composting (aerobic) (Yap and Hadibarata 2022)

*(Kubendran et al. 2017; Ravindranath et al. 2010),

- Open dumping

1. Only protein denaturation has been considered. The emissions have been calculated solely based on the **methane production from 1 ton of leather waste** (Menikpura and Premakumara 2021; Scharff and Jacobs 2006).

- Pyrolysis

1. Pyrolysis is a process where organic materials are **heated without oxygen**, breaking them down into gases, liquids (bio-oils), and solid residues like char, used for making biofuels and chemicals (Yilmaz et al. 2007).
2. In the current study, fleshings, chrome shavings, buffing dust, and finished trimmings were considered to examine output yield and energy production.

- Incineration

1. Considering incineration as a optimal solution for leather waste in waste-to-energy (WtE) plant, which can **reduce mass** up to 93% with chrome waste, like shavings (CS) and finished trimmings (FTW), with 7% incinerated ash (Velusamy et al. 2020).
2. Only heat production has been calculated for post-tanning waste.

Possible treatments for mass/product recovery

- **Gelatin** (mixture of peptides and proteins) is made from the **partial hydrolysis of fibrous protein**, obtained by boiling raw trimmings, lacking collagen's triple-helix structure (Shakil et al. 2019).
- **Biodiesel** can be obtained from **fleshings with 7-18% (fat content)**, followed by neutralization, extraction and transesterification (Sandhya et al. 2016).
- **Keratin** from hair waste offers an optimal solution due to its **high protein content (72%)**, with hydrolysis enabling a recovery efficiency of up to 40% (Ramya et al. 2022).
- Considering **leather sheet and board** from chrome waste can also offer **low-cost composite**, followed by latex as binder (Senthil et al. 2015; Senthil et al. 2022; Senthil et al. 2023).

Table 3. Possible mass recoveries based upon data availability from literature

Leather waste	Mass Recovery
Raw trimmings	Extract gelatin
Fleshings	Produces biodiesel
Hair waste	Recovers keratin
Chrome shavings	Produces leather sheets
Buffing dust	Produces leather boards

Materials and Methods

Materials and Methods

Scope: Finding low emission-based treatments

Boundary Conditions and Functional Unit

“gate to gate”.

FU: 1 ton of waste from a tannery.

Carbon offsets (compensation)

The total carbon footprint (CF) has been calculated as **kg-CO₂eq./ ton** through the whole process.

Figure 4. Boundary conditions for utilizing leather waste (Current study)

Allocation: **Mass (in our study)**, physical properties or economic value

Methodology:

- Extreme events, climate feedback loops, and the interactions between climate change and biodiversity loss.
- Considering **GHGs as emissions** to evaluate the **global warming potential** of each waste with its consecutive treatment, we have adopted **IPCC 2021***, followed by ISO 14040-44 (framework).

Considering minimum carbon emissions ➡ To achieve net-zero emissions ➡ Global action is to limit warming to 1.5°C.

Inventories (Data Collection):

- **Energy input:** electricity (from coal production) in northern India with a CF of 1.71 kg-CO₂ eq./ Input**
- **Heat input:** A CF of 0.0035 kg-CO₂eq./ ton of waste
- **Transportation:** Transported by freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, sourced from the Ecoinvent database
- **Other inputs** for each treatment are sourced from literature, considering physicochemical properties, by-product quantities, moisture and carbon balance, data upscaling, and specific process energy consumption.

(Hoy, Woon et al. 2023)– Curbing global solid waste emissions , (Bogner, Pipatti et al. 2008)– Mitigation of global greenhouse gas, (IPCC, 2021)

**Based on annual production, the input of fuel, thermal efficiency, emissions likeGHGs from ecoinvent

Results & discussions

Results & discussions:

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

- AD process

Figure 5. Model description for AD process as baseline scenario

Input parameters

Waste*	Raw trimmings
Moisture con. (%)	62.5
Total solids (%)	37.5
Volatile solids (%)	59
Biogas yield (m ³ /kg-vs)	0.547

Figure 6. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in the AD process

Results

Loss (%)	1.4
EP (kWh)	275
Heat (MJ)	1371
Digestate (kg)	325

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ ton
CF	373
Carbon offset*	471

Performance: **Efficient**

*Dry basis,literature *Carbon offset=Form of energy*Emission factor for energy in the current study (Arendt et al. 2021; Rinke Dias de Souza, Nariê et al. 2021; Maalouf and El-Fadel 2019))

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

- AD process
- Open dumping

The data has been taken as IPCC norms directly, as leather waste has unique characteristics (Change 2006; Forster et al. 2024).

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ ton
CF	1198
Carbon offset*	-

Figure 7. Model description for open dumping for raw trimmings as a baseline scenario

*(Change 2006; Menikpura and Premakumara 2021).

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

- AD process
- Open dumping
- Gelatin production

Input: 1000kg
of raw
trimmings

Figure 8. Model description for gelatin production from raw trimmings

Figure 9. Overview of the amount of emissions

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF	342
Carbon offset	-
Gelatin recovery (kg)	172 kg

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather_waste	12.044	kg CO2-Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	0.298	kg CO2-Eq
Gelatin	330.340	kg CO2-Eq
sodium sulfite	82.034	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	81.921	kg CO2-Eq
hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	74.083	kg CO2-Eq
sodium bicarbonate	37.343	kg CO2-Eq
ammonium sulfate	25.266	kg CO2-Eq
ammonium chloride	22.711	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	3.880	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 10. Contribution of all flows

Performance: **Efficient** based upon market value of gelatin

Drawback: Requirement of **significant amount** of water

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

- AD & AD + pyrolysis

Followed by
**thermal
drying**

To **pyrolysis**
unit
With 15% of
MC

Using heat to
reduce MC
(**Evaporation**)

Input parameters

Figure 11. Model description for AD and AD+Pyrolysis processes

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste	93.486	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	81.741	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biochar for further use	72.400	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	42.450	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	17.506	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	6.988	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Methane, fossil	4.621	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.834	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biooil	116.869	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	68.524	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	28.259	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	11.281	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Methane, fossil	7.460	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	1.346	kg CO ₂ -Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 12. Overview of the amount of emissions through AD and AD+Pyrolysis process

Model results	AD	AD+ Pyro.
EP (kWh)	275	275
Heat (MJ)	1371	1371
Digestate (kg)	185	-
Loss (%)	1.4	1.4
Biochar (kg)	-	15
Bio-oil (kg)	-	25

Figure 13. Contribution of all flows

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton	
CF	245	283
Carbon offset*	285	285
	AD	AD+ Pyro.

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

- AD & AD + pyrolysis
- **Composting**

Figure 14. Model description of fleshings through composting (turned windrow)

Figure 15. Emissions by processes through turned windrow composting

- Considering optimal moisture balance and carbon emissions, emissions can be expressed as:

$$\text{Total amount of carbon present in leather waste} = \text{Amount of waste (kg)} \times \text{Total solids (kg)} \times \text{Carbon content (\%)}$$

Carbon footprint

Composting	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF*	268
Compost*	528

Performance: **Efficient** based upon market value of compost yield

***(Hashem, Paul et al. 2024)*

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

- AD & AD + pyrolysis
- Composting
- Pyrolysis

Figure 16. Model description for pyrolysis (fleshings)

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste	50.277	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	38.532	kg CO2-Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO2-Eq
Biochar	74.133	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	69.602	kg CO2-Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg	4.531	kg CO2-Eq
Biooil	119.666	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	112.352	kg CO2-Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg	7.314	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, low voltage (IN-Northern grid, electricity voltage transformation from medium to low voltage)	5.638	kg CO2-Eq
lubricating oil	4.285	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	1.354	kg CO2-Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg (GLO, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg)	7.785	kg CO2-Eq
lubricating oil	5.916	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	1.869	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 5E9/year	0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 17. Overview of the amount of emissions

Figure 18. Overview of the amount of emissions emitted from entries

Model results	Pyrolysis
EP (kWh)	7.8
Heat (MJ)	38.7
Biochar (%)	13
Bio-oil (%)	21

Carbon footprint

	*kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF*	257
Carbon offset	13

Performance: **Efficient** in case of mass recovery with their respective market value with minimum energy production

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

- AD & AD + pyrolysis
- Composting
- Pyrolysis
- Open dumping
- **Biodiesel production**

Figure 19. Model description for biodiesel production fleshings

Figure 20. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Fleshings	66.337	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	51.375	kg CO ₂ -Eq
hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	7.676	kg CO ₂ -Eq
ammonium chloride	7.239	kg CO ₂ -Eq
tap water	0.043	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry with reefer, cooling	0.003	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Blodiesel	44.873	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	17.658	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	16.035	kg CO ₂ -Eq
methanol	9.832	kg CO ₂ -Eq
hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	0.601	kg CO ₂ -Eq
ammonium chloride	0.567	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sulfuric acid	0.177	kg CO ₂ -Eq
tap water	0.003	kg CO ₂ -Eq
glycerine (RoW, esterification of palm oil)	22.118	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas	9.577	kg CO ₂ -Eq
methanol	5.872	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	5.864	kg CO ₂ -Eq
hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	0.359	kg CO ₂ -Eq
ammonium chloride	0.338	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sulfuric acid	0.106	kg CO ₂ -Eq
tap water	0.002	kg CO ₂ -Eq
NPK (15-15-15) fertiliser (RoW, NPK (15-15-15) fertiliser production)	66.380	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 21. Emissions through entries

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF*	257
Biodiesel (kg)	93

Performance: **Efficient** in case of biodiesel production with it's respective market value

Drawback: Requirement of **938 MJ** of heat and 54 kWh with auxiliary materials

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

Waste 3. Hair

- **Composting** – Same as case in fleshings, (a static pile composting)

Figure 22. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in static pile composting of hair waste

Performance: **Efficient** based upon market value of compost yield

(Agustini et al. 2018a,2018b, Barrena et al. 2007)

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

Waste 3. Hair

- Composting
- Open dumping
- Keratin production

Hydrolysis of hair waste in the presence of NaOH with a density of 2.13 g/cm^3 (20% of w/v) and water (5 times of waste) at 70°C (Ramya et al. 2022).

Figure 23. Model description for keratin production from hair waste

Keratin production

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Hair waste 1x electricity, high voltage transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3 sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state tap water ■ Keratin powder electricity, high voltage sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state tap water ■ wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 96.725 82.926 11.745 1.841 0.213 68.873 56.528 11.065 1.279 0.000 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> kg CO₂-Eq

Figure 24. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in keratin production

Figure 25. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries

The solid content has to freeze at -80°C to get the crystalline form as output (40gm/l) (Da Souza et al. 2022).

Carbon footprint

	*kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF	160.5
Keratin*	248

Performance: **Efficient** based upon market value of powder yield

***(Agustini et al. 2018)*

- Waste 1. Raw Trimmings
- Waste 2. Fleshings
- Waste 3. Hair

Waste 4. Chrome shavings & Splits

- Leather sheet**

1 ton of chrome waste +
 papermill sludge + water
 natural rubber latex 300 mL w/v
 (density of 60 kg /m³) +
 with 2% ethylene glycol

3*4 feet of sheet
 (16% of the initial weight)

Figure 26. Model description for making leather sheet from chrome shavings

*(Senthil et al. 2023)

Figure 27. Overview of the amount of emissions

Figure 28. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF*	333
Leather sheet	154 (kg)

Performance: **Efficient** based upon market value of leather sheet

Waste 1. Raw Trimmings

Waste 2. Fleshings

Waste 3. Hair

Waste 4. Chrome shavings & Splits

- Leather sheet
- AD & AD+pyro
- Pyrolysis process
- Open dumping
- **Incineration**

Figure 29. Model description for incineration of chrome shavings & splits

- The same reduction is considered, up to 93%, with chrome waste, like shavings and finishings waste, with 7% incinerated ash (Velusamy et al. 2020).

Model results	Incineration
EP (kWh)	-
Heat (MJ)	1085

Carbon footprint

	kg-CO ₂ eq./ton
CF	301
Carbon offset	5.6

Performance: **Efficient** in case of complete mass reduction

- The remaining waste will be managed in the same manner as these four types of waste.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather waste	301.027	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	202.161	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Carbon dioxide, fossil	55.986	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium bicarbonate	22.159	kg CO ₂ -Eq
activated carbon, granular	6.992	kg CO ₂ -Eq
urea	5.172	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry with reefer, cooling	2.808	kg CO ₂ -Eq
fly ash and scrubber sludge	2.705	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Carbon dioxide, from soil or biomass stock	1.960	kg CO ₂ -Eq
diesel	0.741	kg CO ₂ -Eq
bottom ash, MSWI-WWT, WW, average	0.344	kg CO ₂ -Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (RoW, heat, from municipal waste incinerator	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 30. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in incineration

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather waste		301.027	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Furnace		210.751	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Induced draft fan		58.425	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Moving grate		14.556	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Feed hooper		11.303	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Fabric filter baghouse		3.184	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Transport by lorry		2.808	kg CO ₂ -Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (RoW, h		0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 31. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes

Best combinations for Energy recovery

The most optimal treatment for managing leather waste is AD, alone or combined n with pyrolysis.

S1, S2 S4, S13, S14,

Figure 32. Performance of selected scenarios based on the energy recovery

Conclusion

Conclusion:

- The results indicate **efficient energy and mass recovery** from each process through respective treatments.
- Considering **digestate** as fertilizer, the AD process is most suitable with lower CF.
- With a market value and 172 kg output, **non-edible gelatin** is ideal for economic integration, as is biodiesel with a yield of 93 kg.
- Open dumping must be **avoided (high CF)**.

Model scenarios (Raw trimmings)	CFs	Mass recovery(kg)	Performance
AD process	293	325*	✓
Open dumping	1189	-	Avoided
Gelatin production	342	172*	✓
UNIDO 2017	624	-	Comparison

Model scenarios (Fleshings)	CFs	Biochar/ digestate/ compost(kg)	Bio-oil/ biodiesel (kg)	Performance
AD process	245	185*	-	✓
AD+Pyrolysis	283	15	25	✓
Composting	268	528*	-	✓
Open dumping	1189	na	-	Avoided
Pyrolysis	257	130	210	✓
Biodiesel prod.	200	-	93	✓
UNIDO 2017	624	-	-	Comparison

**Dry-basis*

- With a market value and 240 kg output, **keratin** is ideal for economic or medical use (lower CF).
- Considering chrome shavings, AD and sheet production have lower CF values and are ideal for mass recovery.
- Compared to UNIDO CF values, most treatments have higher CF but lower than open dumping.

Model scenarios (Hair waste)	CFs	Mass recovery (kg)	Performance
Composting	160.5	1057*	✓
Open dumping	1189	-	Avoided
Keratin	165.6	240*	✓
UNIDO 2017	373	-	Comparison

Model scenarios (Chrome shavings & splits)	CFs	Biochar/ digestate *(kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
AD process	331	497*	-	✓
AD+Pyrolysis	565	143	235	✓
Open dumping	839.5	-	-	Avoided
Pyrolysis	541	300	490	✓
Leather sheet	333	153*	-	✓
Incineration	301	-	-	✓
UNIDO 2017	221	-	-	Comparison

*Dry-basis

- Considering **pyrolysis for the recovery of biochar and bio-oil** have been found to be optimal as a solution for managing chrome waste.
- However, open dumping should still be **avoided**.
- Creating sheets and boards from chrome waste can also achieve better economic value.

Model scenarios (Buffing dust)	CFs	Biochar (kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
Board	344.5	268	-	✓
Pyrolysis	372	375	151	✓
Open dumping	839.5	-	-	Avoided
UNIDO 2017	221	-	-	Comparison

Model scenarios (Crust trimmings)	CFs	Performance
Open dumping	839.5	Avoided
UNIDO 2017	221	Comparison

:

Model scenarios (Finished trimmings)	CFs	Biochar (kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
Incineration	300	na	na	✓
Pyrolysis	541	270	520	✓
Open dumping	839.5	na	na	Avoided
UNIDO 2017	na	na	na	Comparison

*Dry-basis

- This study **explores optimal treatment methods** for various tannery waste types, **aiming to mitigate emissions and convert waste into economically valuable** products.
- Our study is ambitiously and scientifically structured, considering **literature aspects and fundamental support**.
- Using LCA with Umberto, carbon emissions and energy consumption at each waste treatment stage can be assessed.
- Comparative CFs and offsets **provide a roadmap to decide**; for profit, they inform quantity, value, and viability of products like gelatin, glycerin, keratin, biodiesel, and leather board from leather waste, supporting sustainability and economic benefits.
- This study defines environmental **trends** based on CFs.
- **Identifies gaps** between **hypothetical** and **real-world practices**.
- In summary, this study recommends a **proactive approach** and **proposes innovative solutions** to address the environmental challenges of leather waste.

Future possibilities and limitations

Future possibilities and limitations

- Considered exact biodegradable carbon or co-digestion in AD, it can provide exact CFs.
- Analyzed **CO₂ emissions during composting** of fleshings and hair waste; potential to enhance by considering CH₄ and N₂O.
- Reviewed pyrolysis and incineration processes based on literature; potential improvements in CFs.
- Studied **biochar and bio-oil recovery** for enhanced CFs can be utilized further as pyrolysis gas through a CHP unit.
- Assuming **physicochemical balance** for products like gelatin, biodiesel, keratin, glycerin, and leather board based on experimental data.
- Need of ground data for open dumping to get correct CFs.
- Supervised landfill with energy recovery can be considered as leather waste investigation, serving as a model for other regions to improve waste management practices.

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Thank you